

Comparison of thrips management tactics in An Giang Province, Vietnam. Dec 1992-Mar 1993.

Management tactic	Cost/ha (US\$)	Rolled leaves at 3 WAS ^a (%)	Yield (t/ha)
50 kg N at 20 DAS	11	90.7 a	4.5
Flood with water 5-10 cm deep	-	73.1 b	4.8
Flood with water and add 50 kg N at 20 DAS	11	72.2 b	5.2
Spray with BPMC (500 ml ai/ha) at 7 and 14 DAS	6	45.8 c	4.9
Spray with BPMC (500 ml ai/ha at 7 and 14 DAS) and add 50 kg N at 20 DAS	17	45.8 c	5.3
Control		91.3 a	4.8
P		<0.01	>0.05

^a WAS = weeks after sowing.

Crops infested by thrips can look terrible. Applying BPMC reduced symptoms, as did flooding, but neither treatment significantly improved yields. BPMC treatment cost \$6/ha. Farmer education is needed to avoid unnecessary treatments for thrips in the Mekong Delta. ■

Parasitism of brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) eggs by *Anagrus flaveolus* Waterhouse

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With the exception of a few species, almost all hopper species attacking rice in Asia belong to families Delphacidae and Cicadellidae. Egg parasitoids belonging to families Mymaridae and Trichogrammatidae are some of the most important natural enemies that attack these hoppers. High parasitism, particularly by *A. flaveolus*, is often recorded in the field.

We measured parasitism of *A. flaveolus* on eggs of BPH and GLH and determined the parasitoid's preference when exposed to both. We trapped *A. flaveolus* in ricefields and cultured them in an insectary. Females

emerging within 15 h of incubation in the laboratory were released for 24 h into 3-cm-diam, 30-cm- high mylar cages with a 60-d-old rice plant trimmed to four tillers. Each cage was infested with BPH and GLH adults at densities ranging from 1 to 9 per cage with 10 replications.

In preference experiments, mixed densities of BPH and GLH adults at oviposition on caged rice plants were used to test *A. flaveolus* reared on both BPH and GLH eggs. Each density was replicated 10 times. Data were fitted to the random parasitoid equation of Royama (1971) and Roger (1972):

$$N_a = N \{1 - \exp[-aT/(1 + aT_h N)]\}$$

where N_a is number of hoppers attacked, N is hopper density, a is attack rate of parasitoid, T is total search time, and T_h is handling time. Estimates of a and T_h were obtained using Proc. NLIN of SAS.

For preference, data were analyzed using Manly's index α :

$$\alpha = \frac{\ln(n_{i0} - r_i/n_{i0})}{\sum_{j=1}^m \ln(n_{j0} - r_j/n_{j0})}, i=1, \dots, m \quad (1)$$

where n_{i0} is number of items of food type i (BPH or GLH eggs) present at the beginning, r_i is number of items of food type i in consumer's diet, and m is number of food types.

Data fit the random parasitoid equation satisfactorily (Table 1) and showed a typical Holling type II response. Searching efficiency was significantly higher for BPH eggs than for GLH eggs. The handling time for BPH eggs was lower, resulting in a higher plateau of prey attacked. This implies that *A. flaveolus* had a much higher searching efficiency for BPH eggs.

In all cases, *A. flaveolus* showed strong preference for BPH eggs (Table 2). Values of a were always greater than 0.5, irrespective of the relative proportion of BPH eggs to total number of GLH eggs. Host preference switching was also not evident. ■

Table 1. Parameter estimates of the functional response equation for *A. flaveolus* feeding on eggs of BPH and GLH. IRR I, 1993.

Eggs	Parameter estimates	Asymptotic SE	CV (%)	F	R ² (%)
<i>A. flaveolus</i> emerging from BPH eggs					
BPH	a'	3.374	1.515	23.72	95.38
	T _h	0.020	0.002		
GLH	a'	0.046	0.021	109	51.89
	T _h	0.139	0.170		
<i>A. flaveolus</i> emerging from GLH eggs					
BPH	a'	0.766	0.097	18.13	97.47
	T _h	0.015	0.002		
GLH	a'	0.076	0.024	77.41	66.70
	T _h	0.106	0.060		

Table 2. Analysis of preference of *A. flaveolus* feeding on BPH and GLH eggs. IRR I, 1993.

	Preference for BPH, a ^a (x ± SE)	
	Estimated using ratio of a' values	Estimated using Manly's index
<i>A. flaveolus</i> from BPH eggs	0.989	0.981 ± 0.029 n = 87
<i>A. flaveolus</i> from GLH eggs	0.909	0.943 ± 0.004 n = 89

^a a was significantly different from 0.5, p < 0.05.